

FLUENCY-ORIENTED READING INSTRUCTION (FORI): EFFECTS ON THE READING LEVEL OF THE STUDENTS

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ABSTRACT

This study aimed to determine the effects of the Fluency-Oriented Reading Instruction (FORI) on the students' reading levels. FORI is a reading strategy designed to enhance reading fluency through the integration of echo reading, choral reading, paired reading, and individual reading of the students. The study also examined the relationship between the students' perceptions of these strategies and their reading performance. The Phil-IRI assessment tool was utilized to determine the students' reading levels, while a validated questionnaire was employed to gather data on their perceptions of the FORI features. A descriptive-correlational research design was used, and 75 randomly selected Junior High School students were chosen as respondents. Data were analyzed using percentage, mean, standard deviation, t-test, and rank order correlation. Findings revealed a significant improvement in the students' reading levels following the implementation of the FORI strategy, with 21.33% of the participants achieving the independent reading level. Among the FORI features, individual reading obtained the highest composite mean, which indicates that students highly valued the opportunity to select their own reading materials. Furthermore, results showed a significant positive relationship between the students' perceptions of the FORI strategies and their reading performance. These findings suggest that students with more favorable perceptions of the FORI approach tend to demonstrate a higher reading proficiency.

Keywords: *FORI, Echo Reading, Choral Reading, Paired Reading and Individual Reading*

INTRODUCTION

Global assessments and UNESCO reports show low reading proficiency as a major educational challenge and a contributor to worldwide concerns about learning loss. Many countries continue to struggle to ensure that children reach minimum reading standards. This situation emphasizes the need for evidence-based classroom interventions that foster foundational skills. During the last twenty years, educators have increasingly viewed reading fluency as central to successful reading instruction, largely because it enables students to make sense of what they read (Rupley et al., 2020). However, many English reading programs still give it little attention, even though several theoretical traditions—such as behaviorist learning principles, information-processing frameworks, automaticity theory, and Ehri and McCormick’s model of word learning—strongly support its importance (Aldhanhani & Abu-Ayyash, 2020).

At the national scale, the Department of Education (DepEd) has continued to place strong emphasis on strengthening literacy as part of its broader push for educational improvement (Villalva, 2023). Even with this prioritization, many teachers still struggle to help students develop solid reading skills (Abril et al., 2022). When the Philippines joined the Programme for International Student Assessment (PISA) for the first time in 2018, it posted the lowest results in reading literacy (Haw et al., 2021). This stresses the pressing demand for more effective interventions within schools (Canoy & Loquias, 2022). Consequently, the DepEd implemented the Philippine Informal Reading Inventory (Phil-IRI) through DepEd Order No. 14, s. 2018, as a key component of the “Every Child a Reader” initiative. This tool is designed to evaluate students’ reading abilities in both English and Filipino, providing essential data to guide instructional decisions, develop targeted interventions, and determine students’ participation in remediation programs at the school, division, and national levels.

Although numerous studies have investigated the impact of the Fluency-Oriented Reading Instruction (FORI) strategy on students’ reading fluency and comprehension, a notable research gap persists concerning its influence on students’ perceptions and its impact on overall reading development at higher grade levels. Existing literature has predominantly focused on early-grade learners, emphasizing the relationship between reading strategies and comprehension outcomes, while relatively few studies have explored how these strategies affect older students’ reading proficiency, engagement, and confidence. Hence, the current study addressed this gap by examining the effects of the FORI strategy on the reading levels of junior high school students to have a more comprehensive understanding of its applicability and effectiveness beyond the primary grades.

Specifically, the researcher examined the effects of the FORI strategy on students’ reading levels and the relationship between students’ perceptions and its instructional features. She believed that evaluating reading performance through FORI would enable educators to design targeted, evidence-based interventions that effectively improve learners’ reading skills and overall language proficiency.

This research supports the objectives of the United Nations Sustainable Development Goal 4, particularly Targets 4.1 and 4.6, which emphasize improving learning outcomes and ensuring literacy for all (United Nations, 2015).

Research Questions

This study aimed to determine how the FORI strategy affected the reading levels of students.

Specifically, it sought to answer the following questions:

1. What is the reading level of the students before the implementation of the FORI strategy?
2. What is the reading level of the students after the implementation of the FORI strategy in terms of:
 - 2.1. Echo reading;
 - 2.2. Choral reading;
 - 2.3. Paired reading; and
 - 2.4. Individual reading?
3. Is there a significant difference between the students' reading levels before and after the implementation of the FORI strategy?
4. To what extent do the students perceive the different components of the FORI strategy?
5. Is there a significant relationship between the students' perceptions of the FORI components and their reading levels?

METHODOLOGY

Research Design

The study utilized a descriptive-correlational survey design. It was descriptive because it (a) identified the reading levels of the students before the utilization of the Fluency-Oriented Reading Instruction (FORI), and (b) assessed the students' reading levels after the administration of the FORI strategy. It was also correlational because it examined the relationship between the identified variables and the students' perceptions of the FORI.

Research Respondents

The respondents of the study were the Junior High School students of Maningcao National High School who belonged to the instructional and frustration reading levels.

The distribution of the randomly selected students is shown below:

<i>Grade Level</i>	<i>Population</i>	<i>Sample</i>
Grade 7A	27	14
Grade 7B	28	12
Grade 8	41	18
Grade 9	53	17
Grade 10	41	14
<i>Total</i>	190	75

Research Instruments

The researcher used the validated questionnaire and the Philippine Informal Reading Inventory (PHIL-IRI). The self-made questionnaire was the primary tool used for gathering the necessary data, particularly for assessing the reading performance of the students. The questionnaire was designed to identify the reading status of the students before and after the utilization of the assessment tools of the FORI strategy. In addition, it was also used to identify the significant connection between the students' perceptions and their reading level.

To ensure item reliability, a dry run was conducted. Selected learners served as the respondents for the dry run. The items were tested for their reliability using the Cronbach's alpha test to verify the internal consistency and reliability of the items. The tool measured the extent to which all the variables in the scale are positively related to each other, and its theoretical value varies from 0 to 1. Higher values of alpha are deemed more desirable, and a value of 0.70 is considered acceptable.

Following the conduct of the dry run, the computed reliability coefficients for each construct were as follows: word reading (0.862), comprehension (0.870), echo reading (0.850), choral reading (0.788), paired reading (0.896), and individual reading (0.854). All obtained values exceeded the minimum acceptable reliability coefficient of 0.70, indicating that the items under each variable demonstrated satisfactory internal consistency and were therefore considered both valid and reliable for use in the actual data gathering.

On the other hand, the Phil-IRI is a graded assessment tool designed to determine a student's reading level. It uses different passages to see at what level a student reads, beginning with the Phil-IRI Group Screening Test (GST). It is composed of a 20-item comprehension test based on passages meant for each grade. Students scoring 14 or higher (75%) in the GST need no further assessment; however, those with a raw score

below 14 (74%) require additional evaluation. This means that these students might have trouble reading at their grade level and need more tests for the teachers to know and understand the concerns.

In the subsequent phase, learners undergo the Phil-IRI Graded Passages, an individualized assessment utilizing the Oral Reading Test, to identify miscues, record words per minute, and assess comprehension, offering a comprehensive description of the learner’s reading proficiency. A learner’s reading performance is measured in terms of word reading and reading comprehension using the formulas in the next page:

Word Reading Score Formula:

$$\text{Word Reading Score (\%)} = \frac{\text{Total number of Words} - \text{Number of Miscues}}{\text{Total Number of words}} \times 100$$

Reading Comprehension Formula:

$$\text{Reading Comprehension (\%)} = \frac{\text{Total Number of Correct Answers}}{\text{Total Number of Comprehension Questions}} \times 100$$

The Phil-IRI Oral Test, which adheres to the reading proficiency standards specified in the *Phil-IRI Manual* (2018) in accordance with DepEd Order No. 14, s. 2018, assesses the students’ reading levels based on established criteria. These include the percentage of correctly answered comprehension questions and the level of word recognition accuracy demonstrated during oral reading performance.

Phil-IRI Oral Reading Profile

Oral Reading Level	Word Reading Score	Comprehension Score
Independent	97-100%	80-100%
Instructional	90-96%	59-79%
Frustration	89% and below	58% and below

Shown below is the basis for analyzing the students' word reading and comprehension scores.

Word Reading	Reading Comprehension	Reading Proficiency Level
Independent	Independent	Independent
Independent	Instructional	Instructional
Independent	Frustration	Frustration
Instructional	Independent	Independent
Instructional	Instructional	Instructional
Instructional	Frustration	Frustration
Frustration	Independent	Frustration
Frustration	Instructional	Frustration
Frustration	Frustration	Frustration

After interpreting the scores, the researcher used the guide shown in the previous page to assess each participant's reading proficiency. As presented, a learner identified as independent in both word reading and comprehension is categorized in the independent level. However, a learner considered as independent in word reading but instructional in comprehension is described as belonging to the instructional level, and so on.

Research Procedure

After the design hearing, the researcher integrated all the corrections and suggestions provided by the panel members. A letter of request to conduct the study was sent to the Schools Division Superintendent of Negros Oriental, following the endorsement of the Dean of the Graduate School of Foundation University. The approved and signed request was then presented to the school principals and the respective advisers of the students.

The researcher administered a pre-test and post-test using the PHIL-IRI tool to assess the students' reading levels before and after the implementation of the FORI strategy. Three teachers were tapped to conduct the reading tutorials, each integrating the components of the FORI approach. A brief orientation was also provided to the teachers assigned to Grades 7, 8, and 9 to ensure the proper implementation of the FORI strategy, while the researcher personally handled the Grade 10 group. In addition, the

assigned teachers submitted their daily teacher's notes to the researcher as documentation of how each session was conducted.

FORI is a repeated-reading instructional framework designed to support struggling readers by developing fluency and comprehension. The study implemented a two-week reading tutorial utilizing the core FORI components—echo reading, choral reading, paired reading, and individual reading. The intervention was conducted every afternoon after regular classes, with participants meeting daily for one hour before dismissal. During each session, students engaged in repeated readings of assigned texts and responded to comprehension questions with the guidance and feedback of their teacher.

The teachers consistently followed the FORI routine across the four-day cycle. On Day 1, echo reading was implemented by introducing the title, author, and five vocabulary words, followed by a teacher read-aloud delivered with appropriate expression, phrasing, and pacing. Comprehension questions were asked afterward, and the teacher provided corrective feedback when necessary. On Day 2, choral reading was conducted, beginning with the introduction of the text and vocabulary, followed by a synchronized reading of the passage by both teacher and students, and ending with comprehension checks. On Day 3, paired reading was utilized, during which students worked with a partner to read the text alternately or simultaneously, depending on their comfort and proficiency levels. On Day 4, individual reading was implemented to promote autonomy and confidence, allowing students to read the passage silently or aloud before answering comprehension questions independently.

The primary purpose of the FORI sessions was to motivate learners and strengthen their reading skills, particularly in fluency and comprehension. Both pre-tests and post-tests were administered to determine the extent of improvement in reading performance. Each participant was provided adequate time to engage in repeated readings to maximize the benefits of the remediation program. The entire intervention lasted for two weeks and was consistently administered after regular class hours.

During the data-gathering process and distribution of the questionnaires, the researcher explained to the students the purpose and significance of the study. Moreover, the questionnaires were retrieved immediately after the students completed them. The collected data were then tallied using MS Excel and Megastat software, and were subsequently analyzed and interpreted to address the research questions.

RESULTS

The findings in Table 1 revealed that prior to the implementation of the FORI, the majority of the students were at the instructional level in reading at 54.67%, while a substantial proportion fell into the frustration level at 45.33%.

Table 1**Reading Level of the Students before the Implementation of FORI Strategy (n=75)**

Classification	Word Reading Score		Comprehension Score		Reading Level	
	f	%	f	%	f	%
Independent	---	---	---	---	---	---
Instructional	41	54.67	42	56.00	41	54.67
Frustration	34	45.33	33	44.00	34	45.33
Total	75	100	75	100	75	100
Mean	87.80 (Frustration)		61.61 (Frustration)			
SD	5.58		7.56			
Note: Oral Reading	Level Word Reading Score	Comprehension Score				
Independent	97 – 100	80 – 100				
Instructional	90 – 96	59 – 79				
Frustration	89 and below	58 and below				

Table 2 shows a significant improvement in the students' reading level after the implementation of the FORI. About one-fifth of the students (21.33%) achieved independent level reading proficiency, while a proportion of the students at the frustration level dropped from 45% to just 20%. The majority remained at the instructional level but their performance has notably improved. This is reflected in the higher mean word reading and comprehension scores, now classified within the instructional range.

Table 2**Reading Level of the Students after the Implementation of FORI Strategy (n=75)**

Classification	Word Reading Score		Comprehension Score		Reading Proficiency	
	f	%	f	%	f	%
Independent	14	18.67	17	22.67	16	21.33
Instructional	45	60.00	43	57.33	44	58.67
Frustration	16	21.33	15	20.00	15	20.00
Total	75	100	75	100	75	100
Mean	91.11(Instructional)		68.43 (Instructional)			
SD	5.05		10.32			
Note: Oral Reading Level	Word Reading Score	Comprehension Score				
Independent	97 – 100	80 – 100				
Instructional	90 – 96	59 – 79				
Frustration	89 and below	58 and below				

The results presented in Table 3 indicate a notable improvement in the reading fluency of students following the implementation of the FORI strategy. Specifically, the word reading score increased from 87.80 to 91.11, while the comprehension score rose from 61.61 to 68.43. These improvements are statistically significant, as signified by the t-values of 7.976 and 7.959, respectively, with p-values less than .001, confirming that the gains are highly unlikely to be due to chance. More importantly, the effect sizes for

both word reading ($d = 0.921$) and comprehension ($d = 0.919$) fall within the “large” category according to Cohen’s d .

Table 3
Difference in the Reading Level of the Students Before and After the Implementation of FORI Strategy (n=75)

Variables	Before	After	D	t	ρ	Decision	Remark	Effect Size
Word Reading Score	87.80	91.11	3.31	7.976	<.001	Reject H_{01}	Significant	0.921
Comprehension Score	61.61	68.43	6.82	7.959	<.001	Reject H_{01}	Significant	0.919

Note: Cohen’s d Effect Size: Ignored, $0.00 < d \leq 0.19$; Small Effect, $0.19 < d \leq 0.49$; Medium Effect, $0.49 < d \leq 0.79$; Large Effect, $0.79 < d \leq 1.29$; Very Large Effect, $d > 1.29$

The data in Table 4.1 as shown in the previous page reveal that echo reading yields a composite mean of 4.01, with the highest perception indicator being the ability to “follow the teacher’s reading and repeat the passage aloud with correct pronunciation and expression” ($\bar{x}=4.12$) and the lowest perception indicator being the ability to “get immediate feedback from the teacher with regards to the correct pace, and word enunciation” (3.87).

Table 4.1
Extent of Perception of the Students on Echo Reading (n=75)

Echo Reading Indicators	\bar{x}	VD	EoP	SD
1. I can follow the teacher’s reading and repeat the passage aloud with correct pronunciation and expression.	4.12	A	H	0.49
2. I can improve reading accuracy and fluency through associating the word sound and meaning.	4.05	A	H	0.63
3. I can repeat the sentence aloud originally read by the teacher.	4.03	A	H	0.84
4. I can improve vocabulary through engaging in various activities such as unlocking of different words and etc.	3.96	A	H	0.85
5. I can get an immediate feedback from the teacher with regards to the correct pace, and word enunciation.	3.87	A	H	1.06
Composite	4.01	A	H	0.77

Note: Verbal Description (VD); Extent of Perception (EoP); 4.21–5.00, Strongly Agree (SA), Very High (VH); 3.41–4.20, Agree (A), High (H); 2.61–3.40, Moderate (M), Moderate (M); 1.81–2.60, Disagree (D), Low (L); 1.00–1.80, Strongly Disagree (SD); Very Low (VL)

The findings in Table 4.2 as indicated in the previous page show that choral reading received the lowest composite mean (3.96), although it is still within the “High” range. The highest perception indicator was “I can enhance my word recognition and pronunciation skills by listening to my teacher and classmates during choral reading” ($\bar{x} = 4.00$), and the lowest perception was “I can read more freely together with my classmates” ($\bar{x} = 3.91$).

Table 4.2
Extent of Perception of the Students on Choral Reading (n=75)

Choral Reading Indicators	\bar{x}	VD	EoP	SD
1. I can enhance my word recognition and pronunciation skills by listening to my teacher and classmates during choral reading.	4.00	A	H	0.87
2. I can engage in fun learning activities together with my teacher and classmates.	4.00	A	H	0.87
3. I can read the text aloud with confidence together with my classmates.	3.96	A	H	0.83
4. I can improve my reading fluency and accuracy by repeating the text with my teacher and classmates.	3.92	A	H	0.94
5. I can read more freely together with my classmates.	3.91	A	H	0.92
Composite	3.96	A	H	0.89

Note: Verbal Description (VD); Extent of Perception (EoP); 4.21–5.00, Strongly Agree (SA), Very High (VH); 3.41–4.20, Agree (A), High (H); 2.61–3.40, Moderate (M), Moderate (M); 1.81–2.60, Disagree (D), Low (L); 1.00–1.80, Strongly Disagree (SD); Very Low (VL)

The findings presented in Table 4.3 indicate that *paired reading* obtained a higher composite mean of 4.05, with the highest-rated indicator being “I can promote cooperation with my partner by learning together” ($\bar{x} = 4.08$), and the lowest-rated indicator being “I can enhance my comprehension through discussing with my partner” ($\bar{x} = 4.01$).

Table 4.3
Extent of Perception of the Students on Paired Reading (n=75)

Paired Reading Indicators	\bar{x}	VD	EoP	SD
1. I can promote cooperation with my partner by learning together.	4.08	A	H	0.90
2. I can develop my creative and critical thinking skills through discussing with my partner.	4.08	A	H	0.67
3. I can help my partner improve his/her reading skills by listening to me.	4.05	A	H	0.82
4. I can improve my reading by listening to my classmates.	4.01	A	H	0.91
5. I can enhance my comprehension through discussing with my partner.	4.01	A	H	0.80
Composite	4.05	A	H	0.82

Note: Verbal Description (VD); Extent of Perception (EoP); 4.21–5.00, Strongly Agree (SA), Very High (VH); 3.41–4.20, Agree (A), High (H); 2.61–3.40, Moderate (M), Moderate (M); 1.81–2.60, Disagree (D), Low (L); 1.00–1.80, Strongly Disagree (SD); Very Low (VL)

The findings in Table 4.4 indicate that individual reading received the highest composite mean (4.08) among the FORI strategies, reflecting strong student preference and engagement. Among the specific indicators, “I can choose my own reading materials based on my needs” (\bar{x} = 4.16) and “I can relate what I read to my real-life situations” (\bar{x} = 4.13) were rated the highest.

Table 4.4
Extent of Perception of the Students on Individual Reading (n=75)

Individual Reading Indicators	\bar{x}	VD	EoP	SD
1. I can choose my own reading materials based on my need.	4.16	A	H	0.79
2. I can relate what I need to my real-life situation.	4.13	A	H	0.72
3. I can acquire problem-solving skills materials read.	4.12	A	H	0.66
4. I can develop a love for reading.	4.03	A	H	0.80
5. I can focus and concentrate more on the reading material.	3.96	A	H	0.94
Composite	4.08	A	H	0.78

Note: Verbal Description (VD); Extent of Perception (EoP); 4.21–5.00, Strongly Agree (SA), Very High (VH); 3.41–4.20, Agree (A), High (H); 2.61–3.40, Moderate (M), Moderate (M); 1.81–2.60, Disagree (D), Low (L); 1.00–1.80, Strongly Disagree (SD); Very Low (VL)

Table 5 indicates significant positive relationships between students’ perceptions of the various FORI strategies and their reading performance, with all correlation coefficients (r_s) reaching statistical significance at $p < .001$. Among the strategies, individual reading showed the strongest associations with both word reading ($r_s = 0.717$) and comprehension ($r_s = 0.658$), emphasizing its key role in promoting student engagement and learning.

Table 5
Relationship between the Perceptions of the Students to the Different Strategies and Their Reading Level (n=75)

Variables	r_s	P	Decision	Remark
Word Reading Score and...				
Echo Reading	0.659	<.001	Reject H_{o2}	Significant
Choral Reading	0.686	<.001	Reject H_{o2}	Significant
Paired Reading	0.715	<.001	Reject H_{o2}	Significant
Individual Reading	0.717	<.001	Reject H_{o2}	Significant
Comprehension Score and...				
Echo Reading	0.582	<.001	Reject H_{o2}	Significant

Choral Reading	0.654	<.001	Reject H ₀₂	Significant
Paired Reading	0.626	<.001	Reject H ₀₂	Significant
Individual Reading	0.658	<.001	Reject H ₀₂	Significant

Spearman's Rank-Order Correlation at 0.05 Level of significance

DISCUSSION

Reading Level of the Students before the Implementation of the FORI Strategy

The data presented in Table 1 reveal that the majority of the students (54.67%) were classified under the instructional level, while a substantial number (45.33%) were categorized under the frustration level. Notably, no student reached the independent level in either word reading or comprehension. The mean word reading score of 87.80 and the mean comprehension score of 61.61 both fall within the frustration range, indicating that students generally struggled with accurate word recognition and understanding of texts. The standard deviations of 5.58 for word reading and 7.56 for comprehension further suggest moderate variability in students' performance.

This baseline result emphasizes the students' difficulties in decoding and comprehending texts, confirming the assertion of Rupley *et al.* (2020) and Wagner *et al.* (2021) that many learners can decode words but still struggle to extract meaning, resulting in poor comprehension. From the perspective of the bottom-up processing theory (Gibson, 1965), the students were still grappling with the foundational elements of reading, or word recognition and accuracy, which hinders their ability to construct meanings from texts. This situation validates the claims of Nanda and Azmy (2020) that poor comprehension not only lowers academic performance but also affects problem-solving skills and future opportunities. Clearly, there was a strong need for a structured fluency intervention to strengthen the bridge between decoding and comprehension.

Overall, these findings imply that before the introduction of the FORI strategy, most students demonstrated limited reading fluency and comprehension skills, requiring teacher guidance to decode and understand grade-level materials.

Reading Level of the Students after the Implementation of the FORI Strategy.

The data presented in Table 2 show a noticeable improvement in students' reading performance compared to their pretest scores. A majority of the students (58.67%) were classified at the instructional level, while 21.33% reached the independent level, and only 20.00% remained at the frustration level. The mean word reading score of 91.11 and comprehension score of 68.43, both falling within the instructional range, indicate a general upward shift in reading proficiency. These gains reflect improvements in decoding accuracy and comprehension ability, supported by the reduction in the number of students at the frustration level. The increase in students attaining independent reading status suggests that FORI effectively enhanced their fluency, comprehension, and confidence in reading.

The above-mentioned findings coincide with the findings of Mehigan (2020) that the FORI strategy decreases reading difficulty, builds confidence, and improves comprehension and motivation. From the lens of the automaticity theory, repeated and guided oral reading, which is a characteristic of FORI, frees cognitive resources, enabling students to focus on meaning rather than decoding.

The study of Coggins (2023) also showed that junior-high frustration readers are often capable of measurable growth if instruction targets the specific decoding and fluency skills. As supported by Kuhn (2020), the combination of scaffolded modeling + repeated connected-text practice helps move struggling readers from word-by-word decoding toward fluent and expressive reading.

Overall, the findings revealed that the FORI strategy had a positive impact on students' reading development, moving a considerable proportion of learners from frustration to higher levels of reading proficiency.

Difference in the Reading Level of the Students Before and After the Implementation of FORI

The results in Table 3 revealed a statistically and practically significant improvement in both word reading and comprehension following the intervention. The mean score for word reading increased from 87.80 (frustration level) to 91.11 (instructional level), reflecting a substantial reduction in the proportion of students at the frustration level from 45.33% to 20%. Similarly, comprehension scores improved from 61.61 to 68.43, indicating meaningful gains in understanding. Both improvements were statistically significant, with t-values of 7.976 and 7.959, respectively, and p-values less than .001, leading to the rejection of the null hypothesis.

Moreover, the computed effect sizes for word reading ($d = 0.921$) and comprehension ($d = 0.919$) fall within the large effect range, demonstrating that the FORI strategy produced not only statistically significant results but also substantial practical gains in students' reading proficiency. These findings highlight the effectiveness of the systematic use of FORI, which emphasizes repeated reading, oral fluency practice, and comprehension-focused instruction, in enhancing both decoding accuracy and text understanding. In essence, the strategy successfully moved struggling junior high students from frustration toward instructional and independent reading levels, underscoring its real-world impact on reading development. This is supported by Kanik et al. (2020), who believed that a multi-component FORI package, such as teacher modeling, repeated and choral reading, and engaging formats like reader's theater, could produce measurable fluency and comprehension improvements.

Extent of Students' Perception on Echo Reading, Choral Reading, Paired Reading, and Individual Reading

The findings present the extent of students' perceptions of the four components of the FORI strategy: echo reading (Table 4.1), choral reading (Table 4.2), paired reading (Table 4.3), and individual reading (Table 4.4). Overall, the results indicate that students

exhibited a high level of positive perception across all components, as reflected by the composite means ranging from 3.96 to 4.08, all verbally interpreted as 'Agree (High)'.

Among the four components, individual reading obtained the highest composite mean of 4.08, signifying that students highly valued opportunities for independent reading, choice of materials, and personal engagement with texts. The indicators "I can choose my own reading materials based on my need" ($\bar{x} = 4.16$) and "I can relate what I read to my real-life situation" ($\bar{x} = 4.13$) received the highest ratings, underscoring the importance of autonomy and relevance in fostering reading motivation and comprehension. These results are consistent with Krashen's Comprehension Hypothesis, which posits that language acquisition is most effective when learners interact with texts that are meaningful, interesting, and accessible. By allowing students to select materials aligned with their interests and experiences, individual reading not only enhances comprehension but also promotes intrinsic motivation and meaningful language acquisition, underscoring the practical benefits of personalized reading.

Moreover, these findings align with previous research by Attiyat (2019) and Maja and Motseke (2022), who emphasized that opportunities for pleasure reading and access to self-selected materials strengthen comprehension, autonomy, and reading motivation. Additionally, the capacity to engage independently with texts reflects the role of intrinsic motivation in sustaining engagement and fostering deeper comprehension, as highlighted by Barber and Klauska (2020). Taken together, the results suggest that individual reading not only encourages meaningful personal connections with texts but also strengthens independent learning skills and cultivates long-term reading habits that support overall academic growth.

Paired reading followed closely with a composite mean of 4.05, suggesting that collaborative reading activities enhanced peer cooperation, comprehension, and mutual learning. This finding aligns with sociocultural perspectives on learning, emphasizing that social interaction facilitates language and literacy development. These results align with the studies of Thurston *et al.* (2023) and Lee and Szczerbinski (2021), which describe paired reading as a socially interactive approach wherein peer tutoring fosters both comprehension and mutual academic growth. The positive perception observed in this study supports Vygotsky's Sociocultural Theory, which emphasizes that learning is mediated through social interaction. Hence, the students' responses highlight not only the cognitive benefits of paired reading but also its social and collaborative value, affirming its potential as an effective strategy for promoting literacy development in cooperative learning contexts.

Following paired reading, echo reading recorded a composite mean of 4.01, reflecting students' recognition of its value in improving pronunciation, fluency, and vocabulary acquisition through teacher modeling and immediate feedback. This finding aligns with the claims of Rosel (2018) and Knoll (2015) that echo reading enhances not only fluency and accuracy but also social skills like patience and engagement. The results suggest that students see echo reading as a supportive scaffold, helping them associate word sound with meaning and receive immediate corrective feedback. This also resonates with the automaticity theory, which posits that repeated exposure to fluent

models helps students internalize word recognition until it becomes effortless (LaBerge & Samuels, as cited in Aldhanhani & Abu-Ayyash, 2020).

Finally, choral reading obtained a composite mean of 3.96, indicating that students also viewed group reading as a beneficial and enjoyable approach for developing confidence, rhythm, and word recognition. These findings suggest that students appreciated the collaborative and enjoyable aspects of reading with peers, indicating increased motivation and confidence when performing aloud. Similarly, Mendaros (2022) and Sulung (2021) found that choral reading boosted oral fluency, comprehension, and learner enthusiasm. This signifies that while students value peer engagement, the collective nature of the activity may slightly dilute individualized gains compared to strategies like paired or individual reading. Nevertheless, choral reading remains a valuable tool for fostering confidence and prosody. Correspondingly, Fenty and Brydon (2020) claimed that engagement is correlated with reading success.

Taken together, the results indicate that all components of the FORI strategy were positively perceived by the students. These findings suggest that the integrated use of teacher-guided, collaborative, and independent reading activities under the FORI framework effectively supports fluency development and nurtures students' confidence, comprehension, and motivation toward reading.

Relationship Between the Students' Perceptions of the Different Strategies and Their Reading Level

The data in Table 5 revealed that the relationship between students' perceptions of the different FORI strategies and their reading levels in terms of word reading and comprehension. The results, analyzed using Spearman's rank-order correlation at the 0.05 level of significance, reveal significant positive relationships between students' perceptions of all four strategies and their reading performance.

For word reading scores, the correlation coefficients ranged from 0.659 to 0.717, all significant at $p < .001$. The strongest correlations were observed between word reading and individual reading ($r_s = 0.717$) and paired reading ($r_s = 0.715$), indicating that students who had more positive perceptions of these strategies tended to demonstrate higher levels of word recognition and decoding fluency. Similarly, choral reading ($r_s = 0.686$) and echo reading ($r_s = 0.659$) also exhibited strong positive associations, suggesting that these group-based activities effectively contributed to students' fluency development.

In terms of comprehension scores, significant correlations were likewise found, with coefficients ranging from 0.582 to 0.658. The highest relationship was observed between comprehension and individual reading ($r_s = 0.658$), followed by choral reading ($r_s = 0.654$), paired reading ($r_s = 0.626$), and echo reading ($r_s = 0.582$). These findings indicate that students who valued and actively engaged in the different FORI components also demonstrated better comprehension outcomes.

This finding supports the assertions of Capin *et al.* (2022) that students' abilities improve most when teachers integrate skill remediation aimed at enhancing decoding and accuracy, along with instructional supports that make complex texts more comprehensible. Their research emphasizes that effective reading instruction requires a balanced approach, combining foundational skill development with comprehension-focused strategies. In a related study, Erya and Pustika (2021) maintained that reading serves as a valuable learning activity through which students acquire information, broaden their knowledge, and enhance their English proficiency. They further noted that consistent reading engagement allows learners to develop linguistic competence and deepen their understanding of various meanings and contexts.

Further, Rupley (2020) stated that fluent reading development is important to the learners' academic achievement and reading comprehension. Students' abilities improve most when teachers combine skill remediation (to raise decoding/accuracy) with supports that make complex texts comprehensible. Likewise, Lee and Szczerbinski (2021) and Mendaros (2022) explained that echo and choral reading enhance engagement and expression, while paired reading provides social support that fosters comprehension.

Conclusions

The findings of this study carry an important implication for literacy instruction and the implementation of the school-wide reading programs. The significant improvements in students' reading levels following the implementation of FORI stress the value of structured fluency instruction as a central component of effective pedagogical practice, particularly for learners who initially perform at frustration or instructional levels. The school needs to integrate systematic FORI strategies, such as echo reading, choral reading, paired reading, and individual reading, into a regular instructional routine to support sustained development in decoding accuracy, fluency, and comprehension. Moreover, the consistently positive student perceptions of the FORI components suggest that instructional approaches with the teacher's guidance and learner's engagement can substantially enhance motivation and active participation, both of which are critical for ongoing reading proficiency. The observed correlations between students' perceptions and their reading performance further emphasize the importance of fostering supportive and empowering learning environments that encourage meaningful engagement with texts. Collectively, these implications point to the necessity for educators and school leaders to prioritize fluency-centered, learner-responsive interventions, invest in continuous professional development on evidence-based reading practices, and design literacy programs that cultivate confidence, independence, and long-term reading achievement.

Recommendations

In light of the results and conclusions obtained, the following are hereby recommended:

1. **Schools** are encouraged to include simple FORI activities in their regular English classes and to conduct short, scheduled reading sessions each week to support struggling readers. By setting up a basic and consistent fluency routine such as repeated reading, guided practice, and monitored reading time, schools can help improve students' reading skills and gradually develop more confident and independent readers.
2. **Teachers** should regularly incorporate short reading activities in their lessons, using FORI strategies such as echo reading, choral reading, paired reading, and individual reading. By rotating between group and individual reading exercises, teachers can give students frequent opportunities to practice fluency and build confidence in their reading skills.
3. **Students** should spend 10-15 minutes each day practicing reading using simple FORI activities, such as echo reading, choral reading, paired reading, and individual reading. Regular practice with these strategies can help improve their reading fluency, comprehension, and overall confidence in English.
4. **Parents** are encouraged to become more involved in their children's reading activities by following simple guidelines on how the FORI strategy works. They can support learning at home by providing regular opportunities for their children to read and practice the skills introduced in school.
5. **Future researchers** are encouraged to explore other reading strategies that could help improve students' reading levels. They should also examine how the FORI strategy affects students' overall academic performance to better understand its wider impact on learning.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

The researcher observed all the necessary ethical considerations throughout the duration of the study. Since human participants are involved, the confidentiality of information was strictly maintained. The dignity and privacy of the participants were safeguarded, and potential risks to the participants were minimized to the greatest extent possible. Furthermore, the researcher followed the ethical protocols stipulated by the Ethics Committee of Foundation University. To ensure that the research topic was methodologically sound, significant, ethically appropriate and thorough consultations were conducted. Additionally, the researcher maintained a non-judgmental attitude throughout the process to avoid any form of bias. The researcher also acknowledges the utilization of artificial intelligence (AI) as a supplementary tool to enhance the clarity, coherence, and overall academic quality of her manuscript. In particular, OpenAI's *ChatGPT* (GPT-5 model) was employed to refine grammatical accuracy, improve sentence structure and organization, and support the paraphrasing of selected sections. All AI-assisted revisions were critically reviewed and verified by the researcher to ensure that the final content accurately reflects the researcher's original ideas and maintains academic integrity.

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